

The Effect of Collaborative Learning Methods on Students' Cognitive Development

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Article information:

Manuscript received: 11 Oct 2024; **Accepted:** 12 Nov 2024; **Published:** 12 Dec 2024

Abstract: This in the article collaborative study of methods of students cognitive development effect analysis will be done . Collaborative reading is of students collective work through knowledge get process to optimization directed pedagogical approach It is the students makes sense thinking , problems solution to make , creative thinking and critical decisions acceptance to do skills to develop help gives In the article collaborative of methods cognitive in development place analysis will be done .

Keywords: collaborative reading, cognitive development, pedagogy, collective work , education methods , students , cognitive skills , logic thinking , creative thinking

Education in the process of students cognitive development the most important from goals is one Cognitive development of students knowledge get , problems solution doing , thinking and decision acceptance to do abilities increase means Today's education in the system cognitive skills in development modern pedagogical methods , in particular , collaborative study of methods place big Collaborative study methods to the students collective way work , thought exchange and knowledge mutually strengthening enable creates

Collaborative study of methods effectiveness of students cognitive development has been effect many scientific in studies emphasized.

Collaborative study methods collective work through to the students new knowledge to master help gives of students thinking abilities in development collaborative of methods place , especially of students logical , critical and creative thinking skills in raising how to the results take coming important of students cognitive development help to give for pedagogical in practice collaborative methods efficient of application scientific the basics create important

Collaborative study methods - this of students learning in the process to each other help to give , idea exchange and collective to work based on are methods . This methods to the students only knowledge to learn help doesn't give , maybe their cognitive , social and emotional is also positive for development effect shows . Collaborative study students to communication , own thoughts to express , problems solution in doing collective to work encourages , this while their **cognitive development** big help gives

Collaborative study methods education in the process students together to work therefore , knowledge mutually exchange , problems solution to do and together solutions to find enable creates This of methods one how many useful aspects available , of them some of them below we bring :

1. Logical and critical thinking develops

Collaborative study methods of students makes sense and critical thinking skills to develop help gives Students mutually thought exchange , debate take to go and others by given thoughts analysis to do through thinking processes they deepen . In this they are cause and effect relationships determination , decision acceptance in doing critical the approach to develop they learned

2. Creative thinking increases

Collaborative in the environment students own thoughts to others present enough and new ideas with they come out . It's theirs creative thinking abilities because increases students different different approaches to see and to problems creative solutions offer reach opportunity have will be Each student his own unique his opinion to the team present that 's enough while the group new to views take will come

3. Cooperative and social skills develops

Collaborative study in the process students collective work , mutual help to give and own thoughts others with discussion to do they learn This is his in turn , social skills develops because students mutually in touch will be , communication they do and others with together to work they learn In the team work through students responsibility share problems together solution make , of others his opinion listening and own thoughts efficient respectively to express skills they absorb .

4. Motivation increases

Collaborative study methods students to learn encourages and in them learning to the process relatively interest increases . In the team work , mutual thought exchange , to others help to give and together to achievements reach to the students of learning interesting and efficient that it is shows . This is his in turn , their to learn has been motivation increases .

5. Problems solution to do skills develops

Collaborative study in methods students collective respectively problems solution they try to do . In this they are different different ideas and approaches with they come out , own knowledge to each other present enough and solutions together work they come out . This is the process in students problems efficient solution to do and different different to situations adaptation skills develops .

6. Knowledge strengthening and to master improves

Collaborative study methods through students own knowledge to others explaining to them own thoughts statement they do This is the process to the students own knowledge to strengthen and better to master help gives Students to each other explanation through themselves more more they understand and knowledge they deepen .

7. Himself evaluation and reflection skills develops

Collaborative study in the process students mutually thought they exchange and they evaluate each other . And this in students himself evaluation and own activities analysis to do skills develops . They are their own successes and disadvantages understand themselves as well and others evaluation through changes they enter .

8. Modern technologies with integration to do enable creates

Collaborative study methods modern technologies using more more efficient done increase can For example , online platforms , video conferences , forums and another electron tools through students each other with remote respectively in collaboration their performance can This is his in turn , to the students modern technologies learning and of them efficient use opportunity creates

9. Diversity(civility). Develops

Collaborative study methods different cultures and thoughts unites Students between different thought and of approaches discussion their more open thoughtful to be , others to listen and respect to do take will come That's a lot civility and to diversity positive effect does

Summary:

Collaborative study methods education in the process to the students not only knowledge study , maybe creative thinking , critical thinking , logical thinking and social skills to develop help gives This methods of students knowledge get process activates and them independent to thinking encourages . Education in the system collaborative of the methods efficient use of students cognitive potential more to develop help gives

Collaborative study not only of students mental potential develops, perhaps them social and emotional It also strengthens it while education of the process efficiency increases .

Education in the system collaborative study of methods wide application of students problems solution in doing ability increases and in the future successful social and professional activities prepares

Used literature:

1. Toshmuhammadov, T. (2020). *Ta'limda innovatsion metodlar va texnologiyalar*. Toshkent: O'zbekiston ta'lim markazi.
2. Mansurov, K. (2017). *Kognitiv rivojlanish va uning ta'lim jarayonidagi o'rni*. Toshkent: Fan va texnologiya.
3. Yusupov, A. (2019). *O'qitishda kollaborativ yondoshuvlar: metod va amaliyot*. Toshkent: Xalq ta'limi nashriyoti.
4. Qosimova, O., & Jaxbarov, O. (2022). PEDAGOG XOTIN-QIZLAR SHAXSIGA QO'YILADIGAN PEDOGOGIK PSIXOLOGIK TALABLAR. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 22, 643-645.
5. Khudoynazarovna, K. O., & Ulugbek, M. (2022). TOLERANCE AS AN IMPORTANT MORAL CATEGORY. *International Journal of Intellectual Cultural Heritage*, 2(2), 148-152.
6. KHUDOYNAZAROVNA, K. O. (2022). THE TECHNOLOGY OF ORGANIZING EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITIES FOR THE FORMATION OF THE PERSONAL SPIRITUALITY OF THE FUTURE TEACHER. *International Journal of Philosophical Studies and Social Sciences*, 2(3), 278-287.
7. KHUDOYNAZAROVNA, K. O., SEVARA, K., & RUKHSORA, M. (2022). STUDYING THE PSYCHOLOGICAL BASIS OF NATIONAL CONCEPT OF PERSONALITY. *International Journal of Philosophical Studies and Social Sciences*, 2(3), 265-271.
8. Xudoynazarovna, Q. O. (2022). PEDAGOG XOTIN-QIZLARNING TALABALAR XULQ-ATVORIGA TA'SIR ETUVCHI OMILLARNI TUSHUNISHI: SAMARALI O'QITISH KALITI. *BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(4), 272-278.
9. Khudoynazarovna, K. O., & Kizi, S. N. K. (2022). The Impact of Negative Facts on the Spiritual Appearance of Girls is A Problem.
10. Xudoynazarovna, Q. O. Bobomurod o 'g 'li, BB, & Jaloliddin O'roz o 'g, N.(2022). Increasing the Social Activity of Female Teachers is the Need of the Hour. *Vital Annex: International Journal of Novel Research in Advanced Sciences*, 1(6), 137-139
11. Xudoynazarovna, Q. O. (2022). Technology Of Development Of Social Activity Of Female Pedagogues In The Conditions Of The New Renaissance. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 6(9), 4469-4471.

12. Xudoynazarovna, Q. O. (2022). The Role of Innovative Technologies in the Quality Organization of the Educational Process of Female Teachers. *Vital Annex: International Journal of Novel Research in Advanced Sciences*, 1(6), 133-136.
13. Qosimova, O., & Mamarasulov, U. (2022). THE ROLE OF PEDAGOGIC WOMEN AND GIRLS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THINKING OF YOUNG PEOPLE. *Science and innovation*, 1(B8), 2392-2397.
14. Xudoynazarovna, Q. O., & Qurbonovich-Docent, U. U. (2022). DEVELOPMENT OF TEACHER'S SPIRITUAL IMAGE. *International Journal of Early Childhood Special Education*, 14(6).
15. Xudoynazarovna, Q. O., & Qurbonovich, U. U. (2022). A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE MAIN MOTIVATIONS FOR INCREASING THE QUALIFICATION OF TEACHER-WOMEN AND TEACHER-MALE. *International Journal of Early Childhood Special Education*, 14(3).
16. Utanov Utkir Qurbonovich, X. L. A. qizi . (2023). THE ROLE OF MUSIC IN MEDICINE AND THE ISSUES OF ITS INFLUENCE ON HUMAN PSYCHOLOGY AND HEALTH. INTERNATIONAL BULLETIN OF APPLIED SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY, 3(6), 297–300. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8019314>
17. Utanov Utkir Qurbonovich, A. A. A. (2023). MODERN REQUIREMENTS FOR THE ORGANIZATION OF MUSIC CLUBS IN GENERAL SECONDARY SCHOOLS. INTERNATIONAL BULLETIN OF APPLIED SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY, 3(6), 94–97. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8019320>
18. U.Utanov. (2023). THE USE OF ANCESTRAL HERITAGE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE TEACHER'S SPIRITUAL IMAGE. JOURNAL OF AGRICULTURE & HORTICULTURE, 3(6), 95–100. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8055288>